

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 5*

Compd. no.	R	M.p./B.p.** °C	Yield %
4a	H	80–90/0.25	60
b	4-CH ₃	L	52
c	3-CH ₃	L	50
d	2-CH ₃	L	51
e	4-Cl	L	55
f	2-Cl	L	54
g	4-OCH ₃	L	56
h	2-OCH ₃	L	52
i	4-SCH ₃	L	57
j	4-C(CH ₃) ₃	L	58
k	4-NO ₂	L	55
l	2-NO ₂	L	53
m	2,4-Cl ₂	L	54
n	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	52
o	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	L	51
p	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	50
q	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	L	52
r	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	L	51
s	3-CH ₃ -4-Cl	L	54
t	2,4,5-Cl ₃	L	56
u	2,3,5-(CH ₃) ₃	L	54
5a	H	170/0.25	60
b	4-CH ₃	L	58
c	3-CH ₃	L	64
d	2-CH ₃	L	62
e	4-Cl	L	66
f	2-Cl	L	61
g	4-SCH ₃	L	62
h	4-C(CH ₃) ₃	L	63
i	4-OCH ₃	L	60
j	2-OCH ₃	L	64
k	4-NO ₂	138	65
l	2-NO ₂	L	61
m	2,4-Cl ₂	L	64
n	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	L	62
o	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	65
p	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	62
q	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	L	61
r	Pentachloro	198–200	60
s	2,4,5-Cl ₃	106	62
t	2,3,5-(CH ₃) ₃	L	58

*All compounds gave satisfactory Cl analysis.

**L=liquid; purified by column chromatography.

stirred for 1 h. A mixture of phenol (0.1 mol) dissolved in benzene and triethylamine (20 g, 0.2 mol)

was added to the stirred solution dropwise. After filtering off the amine hydrochloride, the solvent was removed by distillation and the residual liquid was purified by column chromatography on acidic alumina. The purity was checked by tlc over silica gel using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as irrigant. The physical and analytical data of 4 are given in Table 1 : 4a ν_{\max} 935 (P–O aliphatic), 1 190 (P–O–C aromatic) and 1 260 cm^{-1} (P=O); δ 3.80 (3H, d, J 12 Hz, OCH₃), 3.5 (2H, m, Cl–CH₂) and 2.5 (2H, m, P(O)CH₂).

O,O-Bisaryl-2-chloroethyl phosphonates (5a–t): A solution of phosphonyl dichloride (3; 18 g, 0.1 mol) in dry benzene was added to a cold (10–15°) solution of phenol (0.2 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml) containing dry triethylamine (0.2 mol) dropwise with stirring and further stirred for 3 h at room temperature. After filtering off the amine hydrochloride the solvent was removed by distillation. The residual liquid was purified by recrystallisation in the case of solids. In some cases column chromatography was carried out over silica gel. The purity was checked by tlc over silica gel using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as irrigant. The physical and analytical data of 5 is given in Table 1 : 5a ν_{\max} 940 (P–O–C aliphatic), 1 185 (P–O–C aromatic) and 1 265 cm^{-1} (P=O); δ 3.7 (2H, m, Cl–CH₂) and 2.6 (2H, m, P(O)CH₂).

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Synthesis and Biological Activities of some New Acid Hydrazides and their Derivatives†

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Hydrazides and their condensation products are known for various biological activities¹. In view of the above, the new hydrazides have been synthesised and screened for their antitubercular, antifungal and antibacterial activities.

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o-Fluoroaniline or *p*-toluidine on being refluxed with diethylmalonate gave ethyl 2-(*o*-fluoroanilido)ethanoate (1a) and ethyl 2-(*p*-methylanilido)ethanoate (1b). 1b on treatment with aroyl chlorides furnished the esters (4a–c), which when treated with hydrazine hydrate furnished 2-[(*N*-aroyl)-*p*-methylanilido]acetohydrazides (5a–c). 2-(*o*-Fluoro-

anilido)acetohydrazide (2) was obtained when 1a was treated with hydrazine hydrate. Synthetic strategy has been outlined in Scheme 1.

4,5; R' = H for a, o-Cl for b, p-Cl for c
 6; R' = H for a-h, o-Cl for i-p, p-Cl for q-x
 3a, 6a, 1 q; R₁/R₂ = Me. 3b, 6b, j r; R₁/R₂ = Me/Ph,
 3c, 6c, k s; R₁/R₂ = Me/ArOMe, 3d, 6d l t; R₁/R₂ = Me/ArOH,
 3e, 6e, m, u; R₁/R₂ = Me/ArCl.
 3f, 6f n v; R₁/R₂ = H/Ar $\begin{matrix} OH \\ | \\ OMe \end{matrix}$
 3 q, 6g, o w; R₁/R₂ = H/ArOH,
 3h, 6h p x; R₁/R₂ = H/Ph

Scheme 1

Compounds 2 and 5b inhibited the growth of *M. tuberculosis* at 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration only. Other compounds were found to be inactive. Comparative study of inhibition revealed that blocking of the NH_2 group of acid hydrazide by preparation of acid hydrazones augmented antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Jeol-Ex-90 spectrophotometer. All compounds gave satisfactory results for elemental analysis.

Ethyl 2-(o-fluoroanilido)ethanoate³ (1a) and ethyl 2-(p-methylanilido)ethanoate³ (1b) were prepared by reported methods.

2-(o-Fluoroanilido)acetohydrazide (2): A mixture of 1a (4.50 g, 0.02 mol), ethanol (6 ml) and hydrazine

hydrate (12 ml, 80%) was stirred for 10 min when a crystalline solid separated. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals (50%), m.p. 100° (Found: N, 19.82, C₉H₁₀FN₂O₂ calcd. for: N, 19.20%); ν_{max} 3 150 (N-H), 1 665 (C=O) and 1 250 (C-F) cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO) 2.9 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.2 (1H, s, NH) and 7.1-7.3 (4H, m, ArH).

Ethyl 2-[(N-benzoyl)-p-methylanilido]ethanoate (4a): A mixture of 1b (13.26 g, 0.06 mol), dioxane (6 ml), benzoyl chloride (8.46 g, 0.06 mol), dioxane (6 ml), 1b (13.26 g, 0.06 ml) and triethylamine (6.06 g, 0.06 mol) was refluxed for 2 h on a boiling water-bath. The contents were kept overnight and triethylamine hydrochloride formed was filtered out and the filtrate was poured on crushed ice. The solid obtained was recrystallised from 50% aqueous methanol as white crystals (68%), m.p. 72° (Found: C, 69.32; H, 5.40; N, 4.21. C₁₉H₁₉NO₄ calcd. for: C, 70.15; H, 5.84; N, 4.30%); ν_{max} 1 716 (C=O); δ (Me₂CO) 1.10-1.32 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.25 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.0-4.3 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH₂) and 6.95-7.2 (4H, m, ArH).

Compounds 4b and 4c were prepared similarly: 4b (80%), m.p. 64° (Found: N, 4.00; Cl, 10.32. C₁₉H₁₈ClNO₄ calcd. for: N, 4.06; Cl, 10.46%); ν_{max} 1 720 (C=O); δ (Me₂CO) 1.10-1.32 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.25 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.01-4.3 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH₂) and 7.1-7.3 (4H, m, ArH); 4c (71%), m.p. 59° (Found: N, 3.97; Cl, 10.42. C₁₉H₁₈ClNO₄ calcd. for: N, 4.06; Cl, 10.46%); ν_{max} 1 712 (C=O); δ (Me₂CO) 1.10-1.35 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.21 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.01-4.27 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH₂) and 7.0-7.27 (4H, m, ArH).

2-[(N-Benzoyl)-p-methylanilido]acetohydrazide (5a): A mixture of 4a (9.33 g, 0.03 mol), ethanol (8 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (15 ml; 70%) was stirred for 25 min. The resulting white crystals were recrystallised from ethanol, (52%), m.p. 180° (Found: C, 64.32; H, 5.40; N, 13.21. C₁₇H₁₇N₃O₃ calcd. for: C, 65.59; H, 5.46; N, 13.50%); ν_{max} 3 160 (NH) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (DMSO) 2.25 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.15 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.2-4.31 (2H, s, NH) and 6.95-7.2 (4H, m, ArH); 5b (66.4%), m.p. 174° (Found: N, 12.10; Cl, 10.26. C₁₇H₁₆ClN₃O₃ calcd. for: N, 12.13; Cl, 10.40%); ν_{max} 3 155 (NH), 1 665 (C=O) and 1 090 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ (DMSO) 2.3 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.02 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.22 (1H, s, NH) and 6.91-7.2 (4H, m, ArH); 5c (77%), m.p. 187° (Found: N, 12.09; Cl, 10.38. C₁₇H₁₆ClN₃O₃ calcd. for: N, 12.13; Cl, 10.40%); ν_{max} 3 160 (NH), 1 655 (C=O) and 1 080 (C-Cl); δ (DMSO) 2.22 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.08 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.2 (2H, s, NH) and 7.0-7.3 (4H, m, ArH).

2-(o-Fluoroanilido)acetohydrazide of aldehydes and ketones (3 and 6). General method: To a mixture of 2-(o-fluoroanilido)acetohydrazide (0.211 g, 0.001 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.106 g, 0.001 mol) dissolved in ethanol was added a drop of concentrated H₂SO₄ and the mixture was stirred for 5 min. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: 3a (25%),

m.p. 198°; **3b** (54%), 192°; **3c** (95%), 222°; **3d** (85%), 240°; **3e** (95%), 208°; **3f** (55%), 174°; **3g** (67%), 194°; **3h** (73%), 189°; **6a** (54%), 220°; **6b** (49%), 216°; **6c** (95%), 231°; **6d** (79%), 214°; **6e** (95%), 245°; **6f** (32%), 204°; **6g** (84%), 222°; **6h** (75%), 206°; **6i** (66%), 230°; **6j** (89%), 219°; **6k** (52%), 208°; **6l** (65%), 232°; **6m** (77%), 238°; **6n** (73%), 214°; **6o** (67%), 210°; **6p** (58%), 204°; **6q** (58%), 250°; **6v** (98%), 213°; **6s** (89%), 221°; **6t** (56%), 218°; **6u** (93%), 233°; **6v** (31%), 226°; **6w** (78%), 208°; **6x** (67%), 198°.

Antitubercular activity: Compounds **2**, **3g**, **5a-c**, **6c** and **6j** were incorporated into Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium having concentrations of 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and were inoculated with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v strains, incubated at 37° and observed weekly for the growth of organism for eight weeks.

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds **2**, **3b**, **d**, **h**, **5a-c**, **6f**, **g**, **l**, **o**, **p**, **r**, **s**, **u**, **v** were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity by agar-plate diffusion technique⁴. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ using bacteria *S. aureus*, *S. albus*, *E. coli* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria alternata* and *Candida albicans*.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of *N*-[α -(Phenoxy/ Substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/ propionyl]piperazines/ morpholines

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Piperazines and morpholines are very useful in the field of medicine¹. Phenoxyacetic and propionic acids and their derivatives also possess a wide spectrum or biological activities². These results prompted us to undertake the synthesis of *N*- α -aryloxy-alkanoyl-piperazines/morpholines (Scheme 1).

In antimicrobial testing, compounds **1a**, **b**, **e-h**, **k**, **r**, **s**, **v**, and **2b**, **c** and **e** showed good activity against the specific bacteria (zone of inhibition, 9–16 mm) and fungi (zone of inhibition, 48–78 mm, while other compounds exhibited mild to moderate activity. In anti-inflammatory screening), the chloro series compounds **2b**, **c** and **e** were found to show significant activity (% inhibition: 42, 33 and 36 respectively) as compared to the standard drug phenylbutazone (45% inhibition).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a melting apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of com-

pounds was checked by tlc. Structures of the compounds were established by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The title compounds showed characteristic ir bands at 2 900, 1 485, 1 470 (CH₂), 2 900, 1450, 1 370 (C-CH₃), 1 600–1 610 (CO-N), 1 240, 1 010 (-C-C-C-), 1 120 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 2 950, 1 340 (secondary NH) and 1 680, 1 140, 860, 750 cm⁻¹ (substitution in aromatic ring).

The title compounds were synthesised as described below. To a solution of aryloxyacetic/aryloxy propionic acids (0.05–0.06 mol), prepared by condensing the sodium salt of the appropriate phenols with chloroacetic acid or α -chloropropionic acid in EtOAc (50 ml) was added thionyl chloride (0.06–0.07 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for ~8 h. The acid chlorides thus obtained were added dropwise to an ice-cold mixture of aqueous NaOH (5 ml; 4*N* NaOH) and piperazine/morpholine (0.037 mol) with stirring for 45–60 min. The separated amides were filtered and

purified over a column of silica gel using petroleum ether-benzene or CHCl_3 -EtOAc mixture as eluant and crystallised from $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6/\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$.

Biological activities: The compounds were tested for antifungal activity by filter paper disc method³ against *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium crysogenum*, *Trychophyton mentagrophytes* and *Candida albicans* at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. Antibacterial activity was tested³ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi* at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. Anti-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd. no.	R	X	M.p. °C
1a	H	H	59-60
b	H	2,4,6-Br	100-102
c	CH_3	2,4,6-Br	88-90
d	H	2,4-Br	110-112
e	H	2,4,6-Cl	80-83
f	CH_3	2,4,6-Cl	96-98
g	H	2,4-Cl	115-116
h	CH_3	2,4-Cl	98-100
i	H	2-Cl	59-60
j	CH_3	2-Cl	56-57
k	H	4-Cl	33-34
l	CH_3	4-Cl	38-40
m	H	2- CH_3	80-82
n	CH_3	2- CH_3	40-42
o	H	3- CH_3	75-76
p	CH_3	3- CH_3	79-80
q	H	4- CH_3	149-150
r	CH_3	4- CH_3	70-72
s	H	2,4,6- NO_2	89-90
t	H	2- NO_2	260-262
u	H	3- NO_2	190-192
v	H	4- NO_2	105-107
2a	CH_3	2,4,6-Br	90-92
b	CH_3	2,4,6-Cl	48-50
c	CH_3	2,4-Cl	96-98
d	CH_3	2-Cl	55-56
e	CH_3	4-Cl	49-50
f	H	2- CH_3	96-100
g	CH_3	CH_3	80-82
h	H	3- CH_3	101-103
i	CH_3	3- CH_3	76-77
j	H	4- CH_3	130-132
k	CH_3	4- CH_3	68-70

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

inflammatory activity was evaluated by carrageenin induced rat paw oedema method⁴.

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